

Title: From Traditional to Deep Learning: Multi-Site Reliability and Subject Differentiation in Brain Segmentation.

Pedro M. Gordaliza, Yasser Alemán-Gómez, Jaume Banus, Meritxell Bach Cuadra.

Introduction: Accurate volumetric segmentation of brain structures is key for tracking neurological disorders (Gordaliza et al., 2024; Janssen et al., 2022; Sebenius et al., 2024). FreeSurfer (FS) (Fischl, 2012), a widely used reference method for brain segmentation, employs Bayesian estimation for subcortical parcellation and atlas-based methods for cortical parcellation requiring hours to process.

Deep learning (DL) tools like SynthSeg (Billot et al., 2023) enable seconds-long segmentation from raw images and have been integrated into FSv8.0.0. Given this methodological transition, understanding systematic differences between traditional and DL-based measurements is essential for neuroimaging research continuity. Here we assess these differences through a multi-site reliability analysis.

Materials: We utilized the SRPBS Traveling Subject Dataset (Tanaka et al., 2021), comprising T1-weighted MRI scans from 9 healthy male participants (age 25-30) acquired across 9 scanners (81 total images). The dataset's homogeneous demographics and multi-site protocol provide an ideal framework for comprehensive segmentation.

Methods: We evaluated four segmentation approaches: 1) FSv7.4.1 using recon-all with traditional subcortical segmentation and *Desikan* atlas for cortical parcellation; 2) FSv8.0.0 default, which replaces FSv7.4.1's traditional registration and skull-stripping with DL-based SynthMorph (Hoffmann et al., 2022) and SynthStrip (Hoopes et al., 2022) respectively, and implements SynthSegv2.0.0 for subcortical segmentation; 3) FSv8.0.0_{robust}, using the same pipeline but with SynthSegv2.0.0's robust option (SynthSeg+); 4) direct application of SynthSeg⁺ on raw images for complete brain segmentation. All approaches generated volumes for 101 brain regions (68 cortical, 33 subcortical).

Statistical Analysis: Algorithm comparisons were conducted using two approaches: 1) pairwise regional volume comparisons across 81 images with Wilcoxon signed-rank tests and Bonferroni correction ($p < 0.05$), along with concordance assessment via Spearman's correlation and Bland-Altman analysis; 2) segmentation reliability was evaluated through within-subject reproducibility (coefficient of variation, CV, across scanner sites) and between-subject discriminability metrics. For discriminability, we averaged pairwise between-subject Kendall's τ distance (0-1). These metrics were combined into a between/within, τ /CV ratio, to assess each algorithm's overall performance per region.

Results: Pairwise comparisons (Fig. 1a) between FSv7.4.1 and DL-based methods revealed significant volumetric differences ($p < 0.05$). In summary, cortical regions showed differences in 46%, 49%, and 96% of cases for FSv8.0.0, FSv8.0.0_{robust}, and SynthSeg+, respectively, with the majority (18, 21, and 60 regions) being highly significant ($p < 0.001$). Methods using

FSv8.0.0 and SynthSeg consistently showed differences in temporal regions. A higher difference was found in subcortical regions, with significant differences in 82%, 88%, and 85% of the regions (see Fig. 2a for the left thalamus). Fig. 1b depicts that SynthSeg⁺ achieved superior τ /CV ratios in 68 regions, compared to 17 for FSv8.0.0, 9 for FSv7.4.1, and 7 for FSv8.0.0_{robust}. Fig. 2b highlights the 10 regions with best ratios showing significant differences for SynthSeg⁺. Complementary region-wise analyses and supplementary discriminability metrics, for alternative gaussianity and sample size effect assumptions, are available at [shiny app](#) and [Zenodo repository](#) showing similar or stronger tendencies.

Conclusions: Our study demonstrates that DL-based approaches, particularly SynthSeg⁺, significantly improve brain segmentation reliability, notably in temporal regions where traditional FreeSurfer segmentation faces known limitations due to partial volume effects. These substantial differences between traditional and DL-based measurements require careful interpretation when pooling studies across methodologies while offering enhanced capability to detect structural differences in both existing and future neuroimaging research, particularly for subtle pathological alterations.

References:

- Billot, B., Magdamo, C., Cheng, Y., Arnold, S. E., Das, S., & Iglesias, J. E. (2023). Robust machine learning segmentation for large-scale analysis of heterogeneous clinical brain MRI datasets. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 120(9), e2216399120. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2216399120>
- Fischl, B. (2012). FreeSurfer. *NeuroImage*, 62(2), 774–781. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.NEUROIMAGE.2012.01.021>
- Gordaliza, P. M., Molchanova, N., Wynen, M., Maggi, P., Janssen, J., Banus, J., Cagol, A., Graziera, C., & Cuadra, M. B. (2024). *Towards Longitudinal Characterization of Multiple Sclerosis Atrophy Employing SynthSeg Framework and Normative Modeling* (p. 2024.09.17.613272). bioRxiv. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.09.17.613272>
- Hoffmann, M., Billot, B., Greve, D. N., Iglesias, J. E., Fischl, B., & Dalca, A. V. (2022). SynthMorph: Learning Contrast-Invariant Registration Without Acquired Images. *IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging*, 41(3), 543–558. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TMI.2021.3116879>

Hoopes, A., Mora, J. S., Dalca, A. V., Fischl, B., & Hoffmann, M. (2022). SynthStrip:

Skull-stripping for any brain image. *NeuroImage*, 260, 119474.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2022.119474>

Janssen, J., Alloza, C., Díaz-Caneja, C. M., Santonja, J., Pina-Camacho, L., Gordaliza, P. M.,
Fernández-Pena, A., Lois, N., Buimer, E. E. L., Van Haren, N. E. M., Cahn, W., Vieta, E.,
Castro-Fornieles, J., Bernardo, M., Arango, C., Kahn, R. S., Hulshoff Pol, H. E., &
Schnack, H. G. (2022). Longitudinal allometry of sulcal morphology in health and
schizophrenia. *Journal of Neuroscience*, (In press).

Sebenius, I., Dorfschmidt, L., Seidlitz, J., Alexander-Bloch, A., Morgan, S. E., & Bullmore, E.
(2024). Structural MRI of brain similarity networks. *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*, 1–18.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41583-024-00882-2>

Tanaka, S. C., Yamashita, A., Yahata, N., Itahashi, T., Lisi, G., Yamada, T., Ichikawa, N.,
Takamura, M., Yoshihara, Y., Kunimatsu, A., Okada, N., Hashimoto, R., Okada, G.,
Sakai, Y., Morimoto, J., Narumoto, J., Shimada, Y., Mano, H., Yoshida, W., ... Imamizu,
H. (2021). A multi-site, multi-disorder resting-state magnetic resonance image database.
Scientific Data, 8(1), Article 1. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-021-01004-8>

b) Volume Comparison for Left Thalamus

Figure 1. Comparison of volumetric differences across segmentation methods. a) Three-dimensional visualization of volumetric differences between FSV7.4.1 and each DL-based method (FSv8.0.0, FSv8.0.0_robust, and SynthSeg+) in cortical (left and right hemispheres) and subcortical regions. Significance levels after Bonferroni correction are indicated by red ($p < 0.001$), pink ($0.001 < p < 0.01$), blue ($0.01 < p < 0.05$), and white (not significant). **b)** Top: Boxplots showing regional volumes where numbers indicate subjects (1-9) and colors represent different acquisition sites, exemplified with left thalamus. Bottom: Correlation plots (red dashed box) between FSV7.4.1 and each DL-based method with corresponding Spearman's ρ values, and Bland-Altman plots (blue dashed box) showing systematic volumetric differences.

b) Top 10 Regions for the highest τ /CV for between-within-subject ratio

Figure 2. Comparison of intra-subject variability and inter-subject discriminability. a) Brain visualization showing which algorithm achieves the best metric per region: top row indicates regions where each algorithm achieves lowest coefficient of variation (CV, best intra-subject reproducibility), middle row shows regions with highest Kendall's τ distance, and bottom row displays regions with highest τ /CV ratio (best balance between reproducibility and discriminability). Colors indicate the winning algorithm: FSv7.4.1, FSv8.0.0, FSv8.0.0_{robust}, and SynthSeg+v2.0. b) Bar plot showing τ /CV ratios for the top 10 regions demonstrating the highest between/within-subject differentiation, color-coded by segmentation method.